

DataCite Summer Meeting 2012

Towards Next Generation (data inclusive) Publishing

Vishwas Chavan

Senior Programme Officer for CONETNT MOBILISATION
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)

Email: vchavan@gbif.org

14 June 2012

The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)

Vision

"A world in which biodiversity information is freely and universally available for science, society, and a sustainable future."

Mission

To be the foremost global resource for biodiversity information, and engender smart solutions for environmental and human well-being.

The GBIF Informatatics infrastructure

A global infrastructure for the sharing of biodiversity data

GLOBAL BIODIVERSITY INFORMATION FACILITY

SPECIES COUNTRIES DATASETS OCCURRENCES SETTINGS ABOUT

... free and open access to biodiversity data

Welcome to the GBIF Data Portal

Access millions of data records shared via the GBIF network. To learn how to use this site, please see [About](#). To tune this site for smaller displays, see [Settings](#). Version 1.2.5 - [click here](#) to see what is new!

Explore Species

Find data for a species or other group of organisms.

Species
Information on species and other groups of plants, animals, fungi and micro-organisms, including species occurrence records, as well as classifications and scientific and common names.

Example species:
Puma concolor (Linnaeus, 1771)

Explore Countries

Find data on the species recorded in a particular country.

Countries
Information on the species recorded in each country, including records shared by providers from throughout the GBIF network.

See data for:
Denmark

Explore Datasets

Find data from a data provider, dataset or data network.

Datasets
Information on the data providers, datasets and data networks that share data through GBIF, including summary information on 8634 datasets from 299 data providers.

Latest dataset added:
(Table 1) Distribution of planktonic foraminifera from samples spanning the Cretaceous-Tertiary boundary at ODP Site 207-1259

Layout & design © GBIF. Data providers retain all rights to data.

Contact us

Free & Open Access to biodiversity Data

June 2012: Occurrence records (327 million)

■	[0-100] (26,067 cells)
■	[100-200] (4,121 cells)
■	[200-300] (2,178 cells)
■	[300-400] (1,430 cells)
■	[400-500] (981 cells)
■	[500-600] (738 cells)
■	[600-700] (567 cells)
■	[700-800] (437 cells)
■	[800-900] (393 cells)
■	[900-1,000] (324 cells)
■	> 1000 (7330 cells)

10 years of GBIF: Lessons learnt....

- Technology
- Infrastructure

- Capacity Building
- Political
- Social
- Cultural

Trends in Scientific Publishing

Scholarly Publishing

Gray Literature

Patents

Data Publishing

Impediments to data publishing

Lack of
Data Publishing
Framework

Lack of Incentives

Mainstreaming data publishing

Source: Moritz et. al. (2011). Towards mainstreaming of biodiversity data publishing: recommendations of the GBIF Data Publishing Framework Task Group. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 12 (Suppl. 15): S1

GBIF Data Publishing Framework Task Group

Persistent Identifiers

Cross Linking:

- *Data records*
- *Specimens*
- *Sequences*
- *Taxon Names*
- *Authoritative taxonom(y)ies*
- *Scholarly publications*
- *Legacy literature*
- *Multimedia artwork & objects*
- *People*

Source: GBIF (2009) Adoption of Persistent Identifiers for Biodiversity Informatics: recommendations of the GBIF LSID GUID Task Group. Accessible at

http://imsgbif.gbif.org/CMS_NEW/get_file.php?FILE=24d1fe88b849e4225f3117fac03d6c

Data Paper

What it is: Scholarly publication of a searchable metadata document describing a dataset, or a group of datasets

Promote and publicize existence of data

Provide scholarly credit to data publishers through citable journal publications

Describe the data in a structured human-readable form

Data Paper...

Workflow

Source: Chavan and Penev (2011). Data Paper: A mechanism to incentivise data publishing in biodiversity science. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 12 (Suppl. 15): S2

Data Paper....

“The Data Paper is an evolutionary step in ensuring discovery and access of biodiversity data resources over Internet. It will place publication of biodiversity data ...on a par with scholarly publishing”

Lyubomir Penev
Managing Editor
PenSoft Publications

Data Citation....

"It is difficult or impossible given the existing citation metrics system to identify who originally created or added value to the datum"

*Dave Roberts
Natural History Museum,
London*

Please cite this data as follows:

(accessed through GBIF data portal, Mammal specimens,
<http://data.gbif.org/datasets/resource/559>)
(accessed through GBIF data portal, Vertebrate specimens,
<http://data.gbif.org/datasets/resource/541>)
(accessed through GBIF data portal, Natural History Museum
Rotterdam, <http://data.gbif.org/datasets/resource/693>)
(accessed through GBIF data portal, Database Schema for UC
Davis Wildlife museum,
<http://data.gbif.org/datasets/resource/736>)
.....

TODAY

Data Citation....

We need the following elements

for publishers

for datasets

for contributors

for role of contributors

for release & updates

for data volume

for access location

Data Citation....

Two citation types:

- Publisher based
- Query based

http://links.gbif.org/gbif_best_practice_data_citation_en_v1

Data Citation....

Please cite this data as follows:

(accessed through GBIF data portal, Mammal specimens,
<http://data.gbif.org/datasets/resource/559>)
(accessed through GBIF data portal, Vertebrate specimens,
<http://data.gbif.org/datasets/resource/541>)
(accessed through GBIF data portal, Natural History Museum
Rotterdam, <http://data.gbif.org/datasets/resource/693>)
(accessed through GBIF data portal, Database Schema for UC
Davis Wildlife museum,
<http://data.gbif.org/datasets/resource/736>)
.....

Today

Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History (2002 -),
Museum Collection Records. Mammals. 579257 records.

Contributed by Helgen KM (Principal Investigator, curator,
author), Gordon LK (manager, author, curator), Peurach SC
(author, manager), Potter CW (manager, author), Carleton MD
(curator), Maldonado JE (author, developer), Wilson DE (curator,
author), Thorington Jr RW (curator, author, validator), Ludwig CA
(manager, developer, author), Lunde DP (author). Published

online, <http://collections.nmnh.si.edu/search/mammals/>, first
released on 12/02/2002, last updated on 15/09/2010,

doi:17.3377/smi.8.57.965.

Tomorrow

Data Usage Index

“Similar to the Impact Factor for scholarly publishing, a professional recognition mechanism that can also assess the impact of data publishing is urgently required”

*Peter Ingwersen, Professor
Abo Akademi University, Finland
Oslo University College, Norway
Royal School of Library & Information Sciences, Denmark*

Data Usage Index

Data Usage Index
(DUI)

What it is: The Data Usage Index is a measure of the impact of data publishing by being accessed and used by the stakeholder communities

Source: Chavan and Ingwersen (2009) Towards a data publishing framework for primary biodiversity data: challenges and potentials for the biodiversity informatics community. BMC Bioinformatics, 10 (Suppl 14): S2

Data Usage Index....

DUI is computed on the basis of 14 biodiversity data usage indicators

Source: Ingwersen and Chavan (2011). Indicators for Data Usage Index (DUI): An incentive for publishing primary biodiversity data through the global information infrastructure. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 12 (Suppl. 15): S3.

Dreaming of a future....

towards
**Unified
Publishing
Index**

Unified Publishing Index....

Impossible

Impossible is nothing!

International CODATA Task Group on Data Citation Standards & Practices

Co-Chairs

Jan Brase, Sarah Callaghan and Bonnie Carroll

Members

Micah Altman, Elizabeth Arnaud, Christine Borgman, Todd Carpenter,
Dora Ann Lange Canhos, Vishwas Chavan, Nathan Cunningham, Michael
Diepenbroek, John Helly, Jianhui Li, Brian McMahon, Karen
Morgenroth, Yasuhiro Murayama, Soren Roug, Helge Sagen, Martie J.
van Deventer, John Wilbanks, Koji Zettsu

Consultants

Daniel Cohen, Yvonne Socha, Paul F. Uhler

Objectives & Deliverables

- Conduct inventory and analysis of existing **literature and** existing data citation and attribution **initiatives**.
- Investigate and analyze how existing **data repositories** cite and provide attribution to their data sets.
- Identify and obtain **input from stakeholders** in the library, academic, publishing and research communities.
- Provide an **international forum** to identify and help reconcile the needs of various stakeholder communities.
- Share information and create **greater awareness** of these issues internationally.

- Establish a public **web presence**.
- Conduct **meetings and workshops** to articulate the state of the art and best practices in this area, and to identify emerging issues.
- Work with the major international, regional, and national standards organizations to develop formal data citation and attribution **standards and best practices**.
- **Promote scientific data attribution** by developing models, tools, and practical guidance on how to publish citable and trackable data sets.

Schedule of Activities

Completed and Ongoing

- Symposium and workshop held in Berkeley, CA in August 2011.
- Bibliographic inventory and analysis (ongoing).
- Interviews with a sample of identified stakeholders concerning data citation and attribution practices
 - Data Repositories
 - Publishers
 - Researchers
 - Funding Organizations
- White Paper on Current Practices in Data Citation—outline developed.

Planned

- Publish Report from August Symposium and Workshop (May 2012).
- Task Group meetings and White Paper drafting sessions (Copenhagen, DK, 06/12, and Taipei, TW, 10/12.)
- Sponsored Session at CODATA International Conference in Taipei, TW October/November 2012
- Publication of White Paper in 12/12.
- Active dissemination of first phase results in 2012-2013.
- Best Practices White Paper in 2013.

- Further information:
- sarah.callaghan@stfc.ac.uk, puhlir@nas.edu or dcohen@nas.edu

köszönöm !תודה dĕkuji

mahalo 고맙습니다

thank you

merci 谢谢 *danke*

Ευχαριστώ شڪرا

どうもありがとう *gracias*

